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Biased Perceptions of Energy Consumption in the European Union

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Abstract

People's perceptions of the environmental impact of their behaviour play a crucial role in personal decision-making processes. From a policy perspective, it is important to ensure that these perceptions are unbiased and do not underestimate the actual environmental footprint of individual and collective behaviours, as misperceptions may hinder effective action toward sustainability. Based on Eurobarometer survey data from 2022 (n=26,390), this study analyses perceptions of energy consumption in the European Union. We show that, on average, there is a downwards bias in energy consumption perceptions, with a strong tendency to the middle. A third of respondents perceive themselves in the median decile of the energy consumption distribution of their country, with very few believing themselves to be in the lowest or highest deciles. These patterns are consistent across all countries in Europe with some subnational regions revealing particularly high bias levels. We further find that self-perceived energy consumption is a strong predictor for support for climate policies and greater willingness to take personal action to mitigate climate change. We highlight the need for improved future data collection on actual energy use to better identify when individual misperceptions occur and what effects they may have. Improved data will help to evaluate the potential of targeted information campaigns to strengthen public support for decarbonization policies and promote awareness and more sustainable lifestyles.

1. Introduction

Over the past decade, public concern about climate change has been steadily rising. This growing awareness is driven by the increasing frequency and severity of extreme weather events, as well as gradual environmental changes affecting countries across Europe. According to the Eurobarometer, in 2023, 22% of respondents identified the environment and climate change as one of the two most pressing issues facing their country. This figure has increased significantly since 2005, highlighting the increasing salience of climate change in public discourse and policy debates.

These shifting concerns are crucial in fostering support for the necessary transitions toward a more environmentally sustainable society. However, despite growing awareness and recognition of the need for change, many individuals do not adopt environmentally friendly behaviours. This phenomenon, known as the value-action gap, has been widely documented across various domains, including for consumption choices (Nguyen et al., 2019; Peattie, 2010; Wang, 2017; Young et al., 2010), energy use (Momsen & Stoerk, 2014), nutrition (Gifford & Chen, 2017; Haider et al., 2019; Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006), transportation (Anable et al., 2006; Haider et al., 2019), and investment decisions (Paetzold & Busch, 2014; Wins & Zwergel, 2016).

While explanations for the value-action gap have primarily focused on the costs of actions, the significant time lag and geographical distance between environmental behaviours and their consequences, and structural barriers, little attention has been placed on the role of perceptions. If individuals do not have perfect information and misperceive the potential harm of their actions, they may decide not to adopt more sustainable behaviours. Especially in complex decision-making contexts, where limited information is available, this may lead to suboptimal choices that reinforce environmentally harmful practices and slow down the transition to more sustainable lifestyles.

Energy consumption is a prime example of a context that requires individuals to make decisions with only limited information. Individuals often struggle to accurately assess how much energy their lifestyle and activities consume, especially in sum. As a result, comparing one's own energy use to that of others becomes challenging, making perceptions of consumption levels susceptible to biases and misjudgements. These misperceptions can have significant implications for individual and household decisions and the willingness to adopt pro-environmental behaviours. However, there is limited evidence on the extent of these biases, their underlying drivers, and their actual influence on attitudes towards personal climate action and support for climate policy.

In this study, we employ comprehensive Eurobarometer data (n=26,390) for the year 2022 to measure perceptions of energy consumption across countries in Europe. In a first step, we investigate how individuals perceive their own energy consumption in relation to others. Second, we explore the connection between these perceptions and outcomes related to climate action and policy support. Third, we analyse how perceptions of energy consumption are influenced by socio-demographic factors, including age, education, economic status, and place of residence.

Our findings indicate that Eurobarometer respondents significantly underestimate their own energy consumption, with many exhibiting a strong tendency toward the middle of the distribution in their self-assessments. Around a third of respondents perceive themselves as being in the median decile of their country's energy consumption distribution, while very few place themselves in the lowest or highest deciles. These biases are consistent across all countries, with some subnational regions displaying particularly high levels of bias. Moreover, misperception levels are systematically linked to respondents' age, education, and household characteristics. This bias is particularly concerning, as self-perceived relative energy consumption strongly predicts support for climate policies and the willingness to take personal action to mitigate climate change.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of theoretical explanations for misperceptions in energy consumption and discusses previous findings in the literature. Section 3 presents the methods and data employed in this study and introduces our analytical approach. Section 4 presents the findings. Section 5 discusses the limitations of the study and section 6 concludes.

2. Perceptions and their role in environmental decision making

Perceptions play a crucial role in shaping individual behaviour, particularly in environmental decision-making (Saari et al., 2021; Truelove & Gillis, 2018). Three key types of perceptions can be distinguished: First, perceptions of the impact of one's actions as well as the related costs; second, perceptions of personal responsibility and the effectiveness of individual actions; and third, perceptions of social norms and the behaviours of others, which can influence one's own actions through social comparison and conformity. Perceptions can often be distorted by cognitive biases and information deficits.

Only when individuals perceive and understand the impact of their actions can they make informed choices. Research has consistently shown that individuals who perceive environmental issues as more severe are more likely to take action (Baldassare & Katz, 1992; Drews & van den Bergh, 2016; O'Connor et al., 1999). At the same time, perceived costs can act as a barrier, discouraging action even when individuals recognize its importance (Best & Kneip, 2011; Huang et al., 2020). Moreover, perceptions of responsibility and efficacy—whether individuals feel responsible for environmental outcomes and believe they can effect change—also shape pro-environmental behaviour (Hoffmann et al., 2024).

A less explored but crucial aspect is how individuals perceive their own contributions in relation to others and how this affects their willingness to take pro-environmental action (Constantino et al., 2022). Social norms play a key role in motivating behavioural change, as people tend to align their actions with perceived group behaviours. Research suggests that individuals assess their own position relative to others, and this relative positioning can significantly influence decision-making.

One well-established area where relative perceptions have been extensively studied is income perception and preferences for redistribution. Studies show that lower-income individuals often overestimate their social status, while wealthier individuals tend to underestimate theirs (Alesina & La Ferrara, 2005; Cruces et al., 2013). Additionally, individuals with higher incomes tend to provide higher subjective estimates of average earnings. Importantly, those with more diverse social networks—who are exposed to a broader range of information—tend to have less biased perceptions (Knell & Stix, 2020). These misperceptions influence political attitudes, as perceptions of inequality and one's relative income position strongly correlate with support for redistribution policies (Fernández-Albertos & Kuo, 2018; Gimpelson & Treisman, 2018).

These insights from income perception research can serve as a lens through which energy consumption behaviour can be analysed. Just as individuals misperceive income distributions, they may also hold inaccurate beliefs about their own energy consumption relative to others and about broader patterns of energy use. These misperceptions can shape political preferences and influence people's willingness to support collective action on energy efficiency and climate policy. Indeed, the limited previous research suggests that individuals often have skewed perceptions of which

behaviours are most effective in saving energy and tend to underestimate the energy-saving potential of certain actions (Attari et al., 2010). Additionally, information deficits may hinder the formation of accurate perceptions, reinforcing behavioural inertia and limiting support for energy-related policies.

3. Methods and Data

3.1 Data

As our main data source, we use individual survey responses from the Special Eurobarometer 555, which is the European Commission's second survey dedicated specifically to energy issues. Conducted between May and June 2022, the survey gathered responses from a total of n=26,390 citizens aged 15 or older across all EU member states, addressing questions on a wide range of energy-related topics. The respondents can be subdivided into 230 subnational regions, broadly corresponding to NUTS regions at various levels of granularity. Details on survey implementation as well as meta-data can be found online.¹ The key question we focus on is QA6, with questionnaire text

Let's now talk about your energy consumption. How does your energy consumption compare with that of other people in (OUR COUNTRY)? Please use a scale from 1 to 10, where 1 means 'among the lowest compared with other people in (OUR COUNTRY)', and 10 means 'among the highest compared with other people in (OUR COUNTRY)'. The remaining numbers indicate something in between these two positions.

This question asks respondents about their perception of their own energy consumption relative to the rest of the population in their country. Importantly, only 1.6% of respondents (423 out of 26,390) refused to answer this question or responded they did not know their relative energy consumption. We drop these respondents and will henceforth focus on the reduced sample including n=25,967 individuals. Detailed summary statistics on sample composition by age, sex, educational status and rural/urban status are reported in the supplementary material (Table 1). Note one shortcoming of this question is that there is no specification whether the question refers to individual or household level consumption. We will return to this issue when interpreting results and when discussing directions for future research.

¹ European Commission: Special Eurobarometer 527. Fairness perceptions of the green transition. Conducted by Kantar Public at the request of the European Commission Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion (DG EMPL). Survey co-ordinated by the Directorate-General for Communication (DG COMM 'Media monitoring and Eurobarometer' Unit). Brussels, October 2022. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2767/651172>

4. Results

Most people perceive themselves as “median energy consumer”

Figure 1 shows the distribution of all respondents across the ten perceived energy consumption deciles. Note that in a scenario with perfect information, where each individual knows exactly his or her own energy consumption decile and under the assumption that individuals respond truthfully, we expect exactly 10% of respondents to fall into each decile. This hypothetical scenario is indicated by the horizontal dotted line. Clearly, the observed empirical patterns deviate from this perfect information scenario.

Figure 1. Percentage of respondents by perceived energy consumption decile. Horizontal dotted line indicates 10%. If each respondent had perfect information and responded truthfully, each bin would have 10% of respondents.

We identify two important patterns of deviation. First, there is a strong tendency towards the middle. The majority of respondents (slightly more than 30%) perceive themselves as falling into the median energy consumption decile, which corresponds roughly to the median energy consumer within the respective country. On the contrary, only about 4% (0.5%) of respondents place themselves in the bottom (top) 10% of energy consumers. This implies that a large proportion of individuals misperceive their own relative energy consumption behaviour. Similar “tendencies towards the middle” are well documented in the literature on perceived income and wealth distribution (e.g., Knell & Stix, 2020). To our knowledge, this has not been documented in the context of energy consumption patterns.

Second, on average, respondents underestimate their position in the energy consumption distribution. The average perceived rank is 4.68. Under perfect information, the expected average rank for a scale from 1 to 10 is 5.5. A simple t-test for deviations from this expectation clearly rejects the null hypothesis that the average perceived rank is equal to the expected rank with perfect information (SE=0.01; t-Stat = -77.92). While it is difficult to make statements about the accuracy of respondents’ perceptions at the individual level, this aggregate statistic directly implies an average, aggregate downward bias of 0.82 deciles across all respondents. This downward bias is likely to be the result of a mixture of imperfect information causing an actual downward bias, as well as social

desirability in responses, with respondents preferring to answer in a way so they fall into lower energy consumption deciles.

Perceptions are strongly related to attitudes towards climate action

Figure 2 shows the average responses to several questions related to policy support and individual action by perceived energy consumption decile. The detailed phrasing of the questions as well as the response options are given in the supplementary material (Table 11). The relationship between these variables and perceptions of energy consumption is typically positive and relatively strong in magnitude. For example, support for government energy quotas shows an increase from 55% positive responses to 75% positive responses from the lowest to the highest perceived consumption decile. Even stronger is the notion that one should do more to combat climate change, regardless of the efforts of others, which increases from around 50% positive responses to around 90% positive responses when moving from the lowest to the highest perceived decile.

Figure 2. Scatterplots showing the bivariate relationship between the respondents' perceived energy consumption and their willingness to take action and concerns. Data points are average positive responses to the questions (y-axis) by perceived energy consumption decile (x-axis). Regression line is a bivariate OLS fit including a constant. Shaded areas indicate 95% confidence intervals.

While Figure 2 is clearly correlative in nature, there is substantial evidence that these relationships go beyond raw correlations. In the Supplementary Material (Tables 2-6), we provide several regression tables documenting that the positive relationship holds up in logistic regression analyses of the four binary outcomes in Figure 2. In the regression, the target predictor is the individual's perceived energy consumption rank and control variables include, amongst others, age, sex, education, occupational group, household size, housing situation, economic situation, sentiment toward the EU as a proxy for political beliefs, and a full set of NUTS region fixed effects. A detailed list of control variables and the corresponding survey questions is given in the supplementary material. To provide further robustness to these relationships, we consider an additional specification where the goal is to remove socially desirable responses. For this, we drop all consumers who responded that they perceived themselves to be in the bottom 40%. In additional exercises, we drop all respondents in the top 60%. In further robustness checks these responses are not dropped, but responses above (below) the median are fixed at decile 5. In almost all cases, there is strong evidence that perceived individual energy consumption rank is strongly and positively associated with the outcomes of interest.

This suggests a close relationship between perceived relative energy consumption and important outcomes related to reported individual behaviour and policy underscoring the importance of analysing energy consumption perceptions. These findings are moreover consistent with the broader literature suggesting that perceptions of social processes are strong predictors of individual action and policy support (e.g., Alesina et al., 2018). That said, even after controlling for various potential confounding factors, the causal relationship may work in both directions. For example, individuals who feel personally responsible for supporting climate action measures might simultaneously be more conscious about their energy use, while also perceiving themselves as having higher energy consumption than they actually do. In the discussion section, we highlight steps towards more credible causal identification of such relationships to be tackled by future research designs and data collection efforts.

Perceptions are similar across European countries

Figure 3. Percentage of individuals who consider themselves to be in the bottom 30% (left), middle 40% (center), and top 30% (right) of energy consumers in their respective countries. Dotted vertical line represents 30% of respondents. Dashed vertical line indicates 40% of respondents.

In this subsection, we investigate whether the aggregate European patterns we observe are driven by the behaviour of individuals in certain countries. Figure 3 examines how perceived energy consumption patterns vary across EU countries. Partly as expected due to the wording of the question formulated relative to country peers, there is little variation in patterns across countries. On the contrary, we find that the general tendency towards the middle is very homogeneous across countries. Italy shows the strongest tendency towards the middle, with only 8.5% (6.4%) of respondents classifying themselves in the bottom (top) 30% of energy consumers in the country, while the vast majority of around 85% see themselves in the middle 40% of energy consumers.

Table 7 in the supplementary material provides detailed country-specific results on the average perceived rank, the standard deviation of the perceived ranks, a t-statistic to quantify the significance of downward bias in ranks, the share of individuals that perceive themselves at the median (decile 5), as well as the average squared deviation from the perfect information scenario. With the exception of Italy, there is a significant downwards bias in energy consumption perceptions in all countries. For Italy, the downwards tendency is weakly significant, but weakened due to the very small share of respondents that place themselves in the bottom 30%. The share of individuals that place themselves at median energy consumption ranges from 19% (Netherlands) - already twice the expected share under perfect information - to 37.4% (Czech Republic). The average squared deviation from the perfect information setting is lowest in Finland and highest in the Czech Republic, but generally not varying strongly across countries.

In general, the results suggest that the patterns we observe in the cross-country aggregate broadly hold at the level of individual countries. Additional regression analyses relating the country-specific shares of respondents in the bottom (top) 30 percent and the middle 40 percent to numerous country-level covariates such as GDP per capita or proxies for income inequality show no clear relationship, consistent with the rather small variation observed in Figure 3. Similarly, a simple variance decomposition exercise suggests that more than 95% of the variation in all three

respondent shares is driven by within-country patterns. The following subsections therefore focus on these within-country patterns.

Perceptions follow no clear subnational patterns

Figure 4. Perceived relative energy consumption in the considered NUTS regions. Percentage of individuals who perceive themselves to be in the bottom 30% (left), middle 40% (middle) and top 30% (right) of energy consumers. For visualization purposes, the color scale varies across panels

Figure 4 examines whether there are within-country differences in energy consumption patterns based on the NUTS classification of respondents. In general, the variation across subnational regions is rather large. In certain regions in Spain, France and Greece, all respondents perceive themselves into the middle 40%, and in several European regions no respondents perceive themselves into the bottom (top) 30%, respectively. While there is a slightly increased tendency to perceive themselves in the top 30% in the easternmost regions and in selected regions in southern countries, no clear overall subnational geographical patterns emerge. We explore this further in a regression analysis using country fixed effects, the urban-rural classification of the NUTS region, and indicators for coastal and mountain regions as predictors of respondent shares in the top (bottom) 30% and middle 40% across the EU (Supplementary Material; Table 8). None of these indicators are significantly related to the outcomes of interest. While this does not imply that there is no clear subnational pattern for any particular country in the EU, it does suggest that there is no clear and easily interpretable subnational pattern that holds on average across the EU countries considered. One conclusion from this is that the main drivers of variation in individual perceptions of energy consumption are not simple geographical divisions of respondents, but individual variables related to the socio-economic, demographic and behavioural characteristics of energy consumers. These are explored below in more detail.

Correlation with demographic, socioeconomic and behavioural characteristics

To explore the distribution of energy consumption perceptions within countries, we first consider a simple descriptive decomposition of energy consumption perceptions by age, sex, and education. The results are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, both of which show the proportion of respondents who consider themselves to be in the top (bottom) 30% or middle 40% of energy consumers. Three observations stand out. First, there is a clear age gradient in the sense that older individuals (or equivalently, older cohorts) tend to have a higher probability of classifying themselves in the bottom 30% of consumers and a lower probability of classifying themselves in the middle 40%. Second, we observe a similarly significant educational gradient in perceptions, with individuals in the lowest educational group having a lower probability of perceiving themselves in the middle 40% and an increased probability of seeing themselves in the bottom 30% of energy consumers. Third, the sex differences we observe in this baseline exercise are rather negligible. Note that compared to the aggregate patterns per country, the age-sex-education specific patterns cannot be directly translated into average downward or upward biases in the respective subgroups. Only for the overall aggregate do we know the expected pattern and expected rank under perfect information, while the expected patterns by subpopulation under perfect information remain unknown in the absence of actual energy consumption measurements (see the discussion section).

To explore in more detail the potential determinants and drivers of individual perceived energy consumption rank, we estimate three logistic regression models where the outcomes are binary indicators for individuals perceiving themselves into the bottom 30%, top 30% and the middle 40%, respectively. We assume these categories broadly categorize respondents that perceive themselves relatively low, in the middle, or relatively high in the energy consumption distribution. As potential predictors, we use a number of variables derived from the Eurobarometer survey, including socio-demographics such as age, sex and education, living conditions, an occupational classification, proxies for the respondent's economic situation (e.g., difficulty paying bills, housing situation) as well as behavioural characteristics (respondents do not use public transport, but report that public transport is available) and attitudes towards the European Union (Table 12).

The results suggest that both the documented educational and age gradients persist in the presence of additional controls. The sex differential is more pronounced, suggesting that female respondents are slightly more likely to perceive themselves in the middle 40% relative to the bottom 30%, all else held equal. Various proxies for a respondents' economic situation (including whether respondents are struggling to pay bills, whether they own a home, whether they own a car, whether they rent, etc.) suggest that individuals in higher economic positions are less likely to perceive themselves as being in the bottom 30%. Similar traces of rationality can be found when examining behavioural variables, such as whether the respondent uses a car to get to work when public transportation is available, which have a strong negative impact on the likelihood of seeing themselves in the bottom 30% of energy users. Interestingly, whether respondents have negative sentiment towards the EU strongly predicts a perceived position in the bottom 30% of energy consumers. Detailed results of these regressions can be found in the supplementary material (Table 9).

Two additional observations are worth highlighting. First, both household-level variables (such as household size) and individual-level behaviours and characteristics are strongly related to perceptions of energy consumption. This suggests that respondents consider both the household and individual levels when answering the question at hand, which does not specify individual or household level consumption. Moreover, most variables modulate perceptions of being in the bottom 30% versus the middle 40%, with less differentiating effects observed for individuals reporting that they perceive themselves to be in the top 30%. These findings suggest a detailed

examination of individual and household level perceptions, as well as a detailed examination of characteristics that predict perceived high energy consumption for future research.

Figure 5. Self-reported perceived energy expenditure by age group, with 95% confidence intervals. The figure suggests that older cohorts perceive themselves as using relatively little energy compared to the rest of the population

Figure 6. Self-reported perceived energy use by education level, including 95% confidence intervals. The figure suggests that less educated people tend to perceive themselves as using relatively little energy compared to the rest of the population.

Towards identification of patterns of potential misperceptions

While certain statements about average, aggregate perception biases can be formulated using the data at hand, an obvious question is whether *individuals* actually perceive their energy consumption decile correctly or not. However, credible identification of respondents who under- or overestimate their own energy consumption relative to their peers requires much more detailed data on actual energy consumption patterns per individual. Such data is typically unavailable and extremely difficult to estimate without relying on overly strong assumptions. This makes it difficult to assess individual-level bias, which could help in the design of targeting strategies to inform high energy users that they are in fact in the top group of energy users. Such a strategy could, for example, lead to increased awareness of personal energy consumption and increased awareness of energy consumption in general.

To explore potential determinants of underestimation of individual energy use, we perform an additional exercise. First, we define a group of respondents who are likely to fall into a high energy consumption category based on their observed characteristics. We make the assumption that 1) car ownership, 2) not struggling to pay bills (as a proxy of economic status), and 3) using a car when public transportation is available, are positively related to actual energy consumption. Therefore, we classify respondents who jointly fulfill all three criteria into a group of "likely high energy consumers" (about 12% of respondents). In a variation of this exercise, we add home ownership as a fourth to approximate the economic position of respondents, which results in about 9.6% of respondents classified as "likely high energy consumers".

To identify respondents who may be underestimating their energy consumption, we construct a binary indicator that identifies individuals who are both "likely high consumers" and at the same time place themselves in the bottom 30% of the energy consumption distribution. By assumption, we consider this group to be "likely underperceivers". We then run a logistic regression model within the "likely high consumer" group and examine whether there are any available covariates that are predictive of "likely underperceivers" within the group of "likely high consumers". Detailed results of these regressions can be found in the supplementary material (Table 10). These results suggest that, on average, "likely underperceivers" live in rural areas, in smaller households and have a negative attitude towards the EU. Interestingly, there is no significant effect of classical socio-demographic characteristics such as age, sex or education. Of course, there are many caveats to this exercise, most notably the strong assumption that the traits we selected are indeed able to clearly identify individuals who consume relatively large amounts of energy relative to their peers. Nevertheless, we include these results in the manuscript as a baseline for future research, even though the strong assumptions required to obtain them must be kept in mind when interpreting these results.

5. Limitations

This study is subject to several limitations. First, the analysis we present does not imply causality between perceptions of energy consumption and relevant outcomes related to behaviour and policy support. The estimated conditional correlations, while precise, remain associative. Relatedly, the cross-sectional nature of the analysis is inherently less robust than a longitudinal approach. In addition, the survey question at the heart of this research suffers from somewhat imprecise wording that does not clearly distinguish between individual and household behaviour. Moreover, there is no clear way to distinguish whether the observed downward bias is the result of imperfect information, social desirability bias, or a mix of both. Based on evidence from related research examining perceived distributions in the context of income, wealth, and intergenerational mobility, which shows the immense importance of subjective perceptions, we conjecture that imperfect information at least plays a significant role. Nevertheless, these questions cannot ultimately be answered with the data at hand or other data available to date.

Moreover, certain potential key variables, such as income, can only be approximated. Here, we assume that the combined inclusion of age, education, housing situation, whether the respondent is struggling to pay bills, and occupational status in our models sufficiently accounts for the general economic situation of the respondents. Another limitation is the inability to infer misperceptions at the respondent level due to the lack of actual energy consumption patterns in the data. Such data are rare at the household level, and even rarer at the individual level. To the best of our knowledge, there are currently no datasets that capture both perceived and actual (or estimated) energy consumption at the individual level.

6. Concluding Remarks

Our findings reveal important patterns in how Europeans perceive their personal energy consumption and how these perceptions relate to climate policy support and personal action. We document a systematic tendency for individuals to place themselves in the middle of the energy consumption distribution, with around a third of respondents identifying as median consumers. This reporting bias leads to a significant aggregate downward bias in perceived energy consumption across all EU countries. Importantly, our analysis shows that individuals who perceive themselves as higher energy consumers are substantially more likely to support climate policies and express willingness to take personal action, suggesting that the value-action gap may be partially explained by biases and misperceptions in perceived personal energy consumption.

Several avenues for future research remain. First, additional survey studies could develop clearly phrased questions on individual energy consumption perceptions and relate them to a more diverse set of relevant outcomes related to policy support and individual behaviour. This would help to establish a more comparable baseline for future research and explore the potential relevance of energy consumption perceptions more deeply.

Second, a highly relevant question for future research is what happens when we "correct" perceptions of energy consumption. One might expect that "correcting" perceptions could increase both policy support and commitment to individual action in the EU, based on the findings that respondents on average have a downward bias in their perceptions of energy consumption, which in turn are positively related to individual action and policy support proxies. However, in order to answer this question with confidence, we need better information on where actual over- or underperceivers are located in the distribution of perceived energy consumption. This either requires detailed data collection efforts on actual energy consumption levels or developing methodology to credibly impute energy consumption patterns based on household characteristics. In addition, more credible causal identification strategies are needed, suggesting survey experiments as a potentially fruitful future research direction.

Finally, the connection between EU sentiment and energy consumption perceptions reveals a potentially important political dimension to these biases – those with negative views of the EU consistently perceive themselves as lower energy consumers, suggesting that energy consumption perceptions may be entangled with broader political identities and narratives. This raises intriguing questions about how climate communication might be tailored to different political constituencies and whether correcting misperceptions might have different effects depending on one's political orientation. Furthermore, the strong age and education gradients in energy perceptions suggest that these biases are not randomly distributed in the population but follow systematic patterns that may require targeted interventions.

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Supplementary Material

Table 1. Sample size and composition by demographic characteristics.

	N	Share
Age Group	25967	
... 15-24	2396	9%
... 25-34	3293	13%
... 35-44	4173	16%
... 45-54	4521	17%
... 55-64	4727	18%
... 65+	6855	26%
Sex	25967	
... Man	12080	47%
... Woman	13864	53%
Education Level	25911	
... Lower Secondary	4343	17%
... Post Secondary	4052	16%
... Primary or Lower	1327	5%
... Tertiary Degree	6826	26%
... Upper Secondary	9363	36%
Urban Rural Status	25967	
... Rural	16265	63%
... Urban	9702	37%

Table 2. Coefficients from logistic regression models. Standard errors in parentheses. Baseline group corresponds to rural males in age group 15-24, lower secondary education, occupation group "Responsible for ordinary shopping, etc.", living arrangement "Owned by you, your household, without outstanding mortgage" and "no"/"not" responses for binary covariates where applicable. "Refusal" or "Don't know" categories are suppressed in the regression table output. + $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

	(1) Feel Personal Responsibility to Act	(2) Support Climate Tax	(3) Support Government Energy Quota	(4) Should do more against climate change regardless of others' efforts
Ranking	0.046***	0.023*	0.041***	0.040***
	(0.010)	(0.009)	(0.009)	(0.009)
Urban	0.054	0.081*	0.074*	0.154***
	(0.039)	(0.035)	(0.034)	(0.035)
Age 25-34	0.035	0.225**	0.031	0.103
	(0.092)	(0.082)	(0.080)	(0.082)
Age 35-44	-0.033	0.155+	-0.065	0.079
	(0.092)	(0.082)	(0.080)	(0.082)
Age 45-54	-0.022	0.097	-0.065	0.029
	(0.091)	(0.081)	(0.080)	(0.082)
Age 55-64	-0.015	0.164*	-0.021	0.091
	(0.092)	(0.083)	(0.081)	(0.083)
Age 65+	-0.086	0.082	-0.064	0.025
	(0.101)	(0.091)	(0.089)	(0.091)
Female	0.360***	0.060*	0.210***	0.530***
	(0.034)	(0.030)	(0.029)	(0.030)
Post Sec. Educ.	0.348***	0.058	-0.097+	0.162**
	(0.064)	(0.056)	(0.055)	(0.057)
Primary or Lower Educ.	-0.532***	-0.327***	-0.336***	-0.101
	(0.083)	(0.079)	(0.079)	(0.082)

Tertiary Educ.	0.528***	0.224***	-0.103*	0.251***
	(0.060)	(0.054)	(0.052)	(0.053)
Upper Secondary Educ.	0.143**	0.100*	-0.004	0.078+
	(0.049)	(0.046)	(0.045)	(0.046)
Occ.: Student	0.244*	0.235*	0.154	0.193+
	(0.120)	(0.109)	(0.105)	(0.109)
Occ.: Unemployed	0.033	0.030	0.218*	-0.047
	(0.106)	(0.100)	(0.099)	(0.100)
Occ.: Retired	0.065	0.154*	0.151*	0.001
	(0.082)	(0.076)	(0.075)	(0.077)
Occ.: Farmer	0.092	0.183	0.343*	0.207
	(0.175)	(0.166)	(0.167)	(0.169)
Occ.: Fisherman	1.211	0.089	0.764	1.098
	(0.790)	(0.582)	(0.697)	(0.703)
Occ.: Professional	0.102	-0.153	0.351**	-0.003
	(0.143)	(0.122)	(0.123)	(0.126)
Occ.: Shop Owner	0.014	0.041	-0.149	-0.167
	(0.124)	(0.116)	(0.112)	(0.117)
Occ.: Business Proprietor	0.022	-0.219+	-0.149	-0.219+
	(0.135)	(0.120)	(0.118)	(0.121)
Occ.: Empl. Professional	0.266*	-0.216*	-0.110	0.100
	(0.125)	(0.105)	(0.104)	(0.110)
Occ.: General Management	0.309+	-0.163	-0.053	-0.096
	(0.172)	(0.133)	(0.132)	(0.135)

Occ.: Middle Management	0.118	-0.122	0.141+	0.064
	(0.098)	(0.085)	(0.084)	(0.088)
Occ.: Employed (Desk)	0.130	0.012	0.119	0.008
	(0.089)	(0.080)	(0.079)	(0.082)
Occ.: Employed (Traveling)	0.002	-0.018	0.130	0.080
	(0.103)	(0.095)	(0.094)	(0.098)
Occ.: Employed (Service)	-0.001	0.077	0.169*	-0.058
	(0.095)	(0.087)	(0.085)	(0.088)
Occ.: Supervisor	0.009	-0.009	0.074	0.112
	(0.139)	(0.129)	(0.127)	(0.130)
Occ.: Skilled Manual	-0.023	0.040	0.208**	-0.059
	(0.088)	(0.082)	(0.080)	(0.083)
Occ.: Unskilled Manual	-0.178+	-0.050	0.207*	-0.026
	(0.106)	(0.099)	(0.100)	(0.102)
House Owned	0.083	-0.122**	-0.062	-0.053
	(0.051)	(0.044)	(0.043)	(0.044)
House Rented (Market Rate)	0.056	0.018	0.034	0.018
	(0.054)	(0.048)	(0.047)	(0.049)
House Rented (Less Than Market Rate)	-0.019	0.137+	0.082	-0.018
	(0.077)	(0.072)	(0.069)	(0.070)
Rent-Free	-0.011	-0.178*	-0.019	0.120
	(0.077)	(0.071)	(0.073)	(0.073)

HH Size	-0.007	0.068*	0.048	0.049
	(0.034)	(0.031)	(0.030)	(0.031)
Struggle To Pay Bills	-0.172***	-0.017	0.071*	0.017
	(0.038)	(0.035)	(0.035)	(0.035)
Negative EU Sentiment	-0.905***	-0.566***	-0.585***	-0.678***
	(0.043)	(0.041)	(0.041)	(0.041)
Car Owner	0.154***	-0.233***	-0.078*	0.023
	(0.041)	(0.039)	(0.037)	(0.038)
Don't Use Available Pub. Transport	0.220***	0.324***	0.375***	0.126**
	(0.047)	(0.042)	(0.041)	(0.041)
Num.Obs.	25788	25815	25803	25826
NUTS FE	X	X	X	X

Table 3. Coefficients from logistic regression models. Standard errors in parentheses. Baseline group corresponds to rural males in age group 15-24, lower secondary education, occupation group "Responsible for ordinary shopping, etc.", living arrangement "Owned by you, your household, without outstanding mortgage" and "no"/"not" responses for binary covariates where applicable. "Refusal" or "Don't know" categories are suppressed in the regression table output. + $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Individuals that perceive themselves in energy consumption deciles 5 – 10 are excluded.

	(1) Feel Personal Responsibility to Act	(2) Support Climate Tax	(3) Support Government Energy Quota	(4) Should do more against climate change regardless of others' efforts
Ranking	0.159***	0.118***	0.024	0.126***
	(0.026)	(0.024)	(0.024)	(0.024)
Urban	0.009	0.098+	0.131*	0.226***
	(0.062)	(0.056)	(0.053)	(0.055)
Age 25-34	0.008	0.127	0.072	0.214
	(0.151)	(0.137)	(0.129)	(0.134)
Age 35-44	0.052	0.007	-0.109	0.069
	(0.152)	(0.137)	(0.131)	(0.134)
Age 45-54	-0.054	0.002	-0.030	0.080
	(0.149)	(0.135)	(0.129)	(0.132)
Age 55-64	-0.100	0.025	-0.052	0.108
	(0.149)	(0.136)	(0.130)	(0.133)
Age 65+	-0.237	-0.062	-0.049	-0.032
	(0.159)	(0.145)	(0.139)	(0.142)
Female	0.360***	0.004	0.236***	0.569***
	(0.053)	(0.048)	(0.046)	(0.047)
Post Sec. Educ.	0.434***	0.092	-0.001	0.163+
	(0.096)	(0.085)	(0.082)	(0.084)
Primary or Lower Educ.	-0.501***	-0.315**	-0.348**	-0.241*
	(0.119)	(0.113)	(0.113)	(0.117)

Tertiary Educ.	0.615***	0.369***	0.111	0.339***
	(0.092)	(0.082)	(0.078)	(0.080)
Upper Secondary Educ.	0.216**	0.165*	0.081	0.104
	(0.076)	(0.071)	(0.069)	(0.070)
Occ.: Student	0.088	0.224	0.091	0.134
	(0.199)	(0.177)	(0.170)	(0.179)
Occ.: Unemployed	-0.244	0.210	-0.005	-0.310*
	(0.163)	(0.152)	(0.149)	(0.153)
Occ.: Retired	-0.088	0.261*	0.005	-0.132
	(0.129)	(0.114)	(0.115)	(0.119)
Occ.: Farmer	-0.115	0.336	0.286	0.187
	(0.289)	(0.273)	(0.278)	(0.283)
Occ.: Fisherman	0.582	0.891	1.336	12.000
	(1.189)	(1.213)	(1.309)	(153.104)
Occ.: Professional	-0.228	-0.172	0.254	-0.289
	(0.229)	(0.197)	(0.201)	(0.203)
Occ.: Shop Owner	-0.061	0.135	-0.284	-0.263
	(0.206)	(0.186)	(0.181)	(0.189)
Occ.: Business Proprietor	0.097	0.088	-0.210	-0.239
	(0.230)	(0.195)	(0.190)	(0.195)
Occ.: Empl. Professional	0.009	0.014	-0.383*	-0.232
	(0.204)	(0.172)	(0.169)	(0.176)
Occ.: General Management	-0.085	-0.161	-0.062	-0.421+
	(0.284)	(0.222)	(0.223)	(0.224)

Occ.: Middle Management	-0.110	0.003	-0.130	-0.125
	(0.163)	(0.136)	(0.135)	(0.142)
Occ.: Employed (Desk)	-0.126	-0.003	-0.149	-0.368**
	(0.149)	(0.128)	(0.128)	(0.133)
Occ.: Employed (Traveling)	-0.212	0.154	-0.040	-0.313+
	(0.178)	(0.160)	(0.159)	(0.162)
Occ.: Employed (Service)	-0.297+	0.267+	0.010	-0.236+
	(0.156)	(0.140)	(0.136)	(0.143)
Occ.: Supervisor	-0.100	0.328	-0.180	-0.114
	(0.243)	(0.227)	(0.213)	(0.219)
Occ.: Skilled Manual	-0.251+	0.141	0.085	-0.229+
	(0.144)	(0.130)	(0.129)	(0.133)
Occ.: Unskilled Manual	-0.497**	0.117	-0.019	-0.201
	(0.167)	(0.156)	(0.155)	(0.160)
House Owned	0.243**	-0.152*	0.079	-0.044
	(0.088)	(0.073)	(0.070)	(0.073)
House Rented (Market Rate)	0.089	0.056	0.085	0.034
	(0.082)	(0.075)	(0.071)	(0.074)
House Rented (Less Than Market Rate)	-0.102	0.043	-0.095	-0.102
	(0.113)	(0.107)	(0.101)	(0.104)
Rent-Free	-0.099	-0.235*	-0.075	0.042
	(0.122)	(0.115)	(0.117)	(0.116)

HH Size	-0.004	0.045	0.133**	0.013
	(0.053)	(0.048)	(0.046)	(0.047)
Struggle To Pay Bills	-0.189**	0.074	0.067	0.126*
	(0.059)	(0.056)	(0.054)	(0.055)
Negative EU Sentiment	-0.943***	-0.483***	-0.555***	-0.783***
	(0.064)	(0.060)	(0.060)	(0.060)
Car Owner	0.213***	-0.269***	-0.034	0.028
	(0.062)	(0.058)	(0.055)	(0.057)
Don't Use Available Pub. Transport	0.146+	0.182*	0.312***	0.137+
	(0.081)	(0.072)	(0.071)	(0.070)
Num.Obs.	10773	10778	10825	10838
NUTS FE	X	X	X	X

Table 4. Coefficients from logistic regression models. Standard errors in parentheses. Baseline group corresponds to rural males in age group 15-24, lower secondary education, occupation group "Responsible for ordinary shopping, etc.", living arrangement "Owned by you, your household, without outstanding mortgage" and "no"/"not" responses for binary covariates where applicable. "Refusal" or "Don't know" categories are suppressed in the regression table output. + $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Individuals that perceive themselves in energy consumption deciles 1 – 4 are excluded.

	(1) Feel Personal Responsibility to Act	(2) Support Climate Tax	(3) Support Government Energy Quota	(4) Should do more against climate change regardless of others' efforts
Ranking	0.050*	0.033+	0.062***	0.045*
	(0.021)	(0.019)	(0.019)	(0.019)
Urban	0.086	0.068	0.039	0.095*
	(0.053)	(0.047)	(0.046)	(0.047)
Age 25-34	0.055	0.258*	0.009	0.028
	(0.120)	(0.106)	(0.105)	(0.107)
Age 35-44	-0.057	0.214*	-0.044	0.082
	(0.119)	(0.106)	(0.105)	(0.108)
Age 45-54	-0.003	0.124	-0.111	-0.014
	(0.119)	(0.105)	(0.105)	(0.108)
Age 55-64	0.022	0.218*	-0.022	0.067
	(0.122)	(0.108)	(0.108)	(0.110)
Age 65+	0.047	0.161	-0.106	0.064
	(0.137)	(0.121)	(0.120)	(0.123)
Female	0.375***	0.108**	0.207***	0.511***
	(0.046)	(0.041)	(0.040)	(0.041)
Post Sec. Educ.	0.257**	0.015	-0.187*	0.154+
	(0.091)	(0.079)	(0.078)	(0.080)
Primary or Lower Educ.	-0.512***	-0.315**	-0.271*	0.075
	(0.127)	(0.118)	(0.119)	(0.127)

Tertiary Educ.	0.425***	0.108	-0.275***	0.174*
	(0.084)	(0.074)	(0.072)	(0.074)
Upper Secondary Educ.	0.062	0.049	-0.079	0.052
	(0.069)	(0.064)	(0.063)	(0.063)
Occ.: Student	0.370*	0.189	0.238+	0.232
	(0.156)	(0.143)	(0.139)	(0.143)
Occ.: Unemployed	0.278+	-0.160	0.394**	0.132
	(0.148)	(0.137)	(0.138)	(0.139)
Occ.: Retired	0.212+	0.076	0.305**	0.102
	(0.113)	(0.106)	(0.103)	(0.106)
Occ.: Farmer	0.301	0.083	0.420+	0.195
	(0.230)	(0.217)	(0.217)	(0.218)
Occ.: Fisherman	1.431	-0.313	0.697	0.688
	(1.077)	(0.679)	(0.847)	(0.784)
Occ.: Professional	0.392*	-0.197	0.448**	0.195
	(0.189)	(0.162)	(0.161)	(0.166)
Occ.: Shop Owner	0.116	-0.050	-0.005	-0.115
	(0.161)	(0.153)	(0.147)	(0.152)
Occ.: Business Proprietor	0.016	-0.433**	-0.071	-0.189
	(0.171)	(0.157)	(0.156)	(0.159)
Occ.: Empl. Professional	0.502**	-0.371**	0.108	0.329*
	(0.162)	(0.137)	(0.135)	(0.145)
Occ.: General Management	0.585**	-0.193	0.014	0.086
	(0.221)	(0.172)	(0.169)	(0.175)

Occ.: Middle Management	0.290*	-0.218+	0.351**	0.186
	(0.127)	(0.114)	(0.112)	(0.116)
Occ.: Employed (Desk)	0.318**	-0.038	0.320**	0.224*
	(0.114)	(0.106)	(0.103)	(0.107)
Occ.: Employed (Traveling)	0.154	-0.151	0.265*	0.300*
	(0.131)	(0.124)	(0.121)	(0.127)
Occ.: Employed (Service)	0.218+	-0.060	0.327**	0.045
	(0.123)	(0.114)	(0.112)	(0.114)
Occ.: Supervisor	0.096	-0.234	0.238	0.184
	(0.175)	(0.164)	(0.162)	(0.166)
Occ.: Skilled Manual	0.119	-0.052	0.326**	0.044
	(0.114)	(0.109)	(0.106)	(0.108)
Occ.: Unskilled Manual	0.099	-0.192	0.424**	0.126
	(0.144)	(0.134)	(0.136)	(0.137)
House Owned	0.011	-0.105+	-0.139*	-0.061
	(0.065)	(0.057)	(0.055)	(0.058)
House Rented (Market Rate)	0.018	-0.018	-0.011	-0.005
	(0.075)	(0.066)	(0.065)	(0.067)
House Rented (Less Than Market Rate)	0.086	0.228*	0.273**	0.070
	(0.112)	(0.101)	(0.100)	(0.099)
Rent-Free	0.043	-0.144	0.022	0.181+
	(0.103)	(0.094)	(0.097)	(0.098)

HH Size	-0.004	0.092*	-0.015	0.081+
	(0.047)	(0.042)	(0.042)	(0.043)
Struggle To Pay Bills	-0.136**	-0.082+	0.088+	-0.049
	(0.051)	(0.047)	(0.047)	(0.047)
Negative EU Sentiment	-0.883***	-0.645***	-0.615***	-0.578***
	(0.061)	(0.058)	(0.058)	(0.059)
Car Owner	0.078	-0.183***	-0.119*	0.046
	(0.059)	(0.055)	(0.053)	(0.054)
Don't Use Available Pub. Transport	0.279***	0.398***	0.415***	0.127*
	(0.059)	(0.052)	(0.051)	(0.052)
Num.Obs.	14850	14856	14861	14737
NUTS FE	X	X	X	X

Table 5. Coefficients from logistic regression models. Standard errors in parentheses. Baseline group corresponds to rural males in age group 15-24, lower secondary education, occupation group "Responsible for ordinary shopping, etc.", living arrangement "Owned by you, your household, without outstanding mortgage" and "no"/"not" responses for binary covariates where applicable. "Refusal" or "Don't know" categories are suppressed in the regression table output. + $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Responses of individuals that perceive themselves in energy consumption deciles 5 – 10 are fixed to decile 5.

	(1) Feel Personal Responsibility to Act	(2) Support Climate Tax	(3) Support Government Energy Quota	(4) Should do more against climate change regardless of others' efforts
Ranking	0.071***	0.032*	0.046***	0.059***
	(0.015)	(0.014)	(0.013)	(0.013)
Urban	0.055	0.082*	0.075*	0.155***
	(0.039)	(0.035)	(0.034)	(0.035)
Age 25-34	0.035	0.225**	0.031	0.103
	(0.092)	(0.082)	(0.080)	(0.082)
Age 35-44	-0.031	0.156+	-0.065	0.080
	(0.092)	(0.082)	(0.080)	(0.082)
Age 45-54	-0.019	0.098	-0.065	0.031
	(0.091)	(0.081)	(0.080)	(0.082)
Age 55-64	-0.013	0.165*	-0.022	0.092
	(0.092)	(0.083)	(0.081)	(0.083)
Age 65+	-0.084	0.083	-0.066	0.026
	(0.101)	(0.091)	(0.089)	(0.091)
Female	0.360***	0.060*	0.209***	0.530***
	(0.034)	(0.030)	(0.029)	(0.030)
Post Sec. Educ.	0.349***	0.058	-0.097+	0.162**
	(0.064)	(0.056)	(0.055)	(0.057)
Primary or Lower Educ.	-0.529***	-0.327***	-0.337***	-0.099
	(0.083)	(0.079)	(0.079)	(0.083)

Tertiary Educ.	0.528***	0.224***	-0.103*	0.250***
	(0.060)	(0.054)	(0.052)	(0.053)
Upper Secondary Educ.	0.143**	0.100*	-0.003	0.077+
	(0.049)	(0.046)	(0.045)	(0.046)
Occ.: Student	0.245*	0.235*	0.156	0.193+
	(0.120)	(0.109)	(0.105)	(0.109)
Occ.: Unemployed	0.037	0.031	0.218*	-0.044
	(0.106)	(0.100)	(0.099)	(0.100)
Occ.: Retired	0.069	0.156*	0.151*	0.003
	(0.082)	(0.076)	(0.075)	(0.077)
Occ.: Farmer	0.097	0.185	0.347*	0.213
	(0.174)	(0.166)	(0.167)	(0.169)
Occ.: Fisherman	1.208	0.088	0.764	1.096
	(0.791)	(0.582)	(0.697)	(0.703)
Occ.: Professional	0.107	-0.151	0.355**	0.002
	(0.143)	(0.122)	(0.123)	(0.126)
Occ.: Shop Owner	0.021	0.044	-0.144	-0.161
	(0.124)	(0.116)	(0.112)	(0.117)
Occ.: Business Proprietor	0.026	-0.217+	-0.145	-0.216+
	(0.135)	(0.120)	(0.118)	(0.121)
Occ.: Empl. Professional	0.270*	-0.215*	-0.107	0.103
	(0.125)	(0.105)	(0.104)	(0.110)
Occ.: General Management	0.314+	-0.160	-0.049	-0.091
	(0.172)	(0.133)	(0.132)	(0.135)

Occ.: Middle Management	0.121	-0.121	0.143+	0.066
	(0.098)	(0.085)	(0.084)	(0.088)
Occ.: Employed (Desk)	0.133	0.013	0.122	0.010
	(0.089)	(0.080)	(0.079)	(0.082)
Occ.: Employed (Traveling)	0.007	-0.015	0.136	0.085
	(0.103)	(0.095)	(0.094)	(0.098)
Occ.: Employed (Service)	0.000	0.077	0.170*	-0.057
	(0.095)	(0.087)	(0.085)	(0.088)
Occ.: Supervisor	0.012	-0.007	0.077	0.114
	(0.139)	(0.129)	(0.127)	(0.130)
Occ.: Skilled Manual	-0.021	0.040	0.209**	-0.058
	(0.088)	(0.082)	(0.080)	(0.083)
Occ.: Unskilled Manual	-0.176+	-0.049	0.207*	-0.024
	(0.106)	(0.099)	(0.100)	(0.102)
House Owned	0.084+	-0.122**	-0.061	-0.052
	(0.051)	(0.044)	(0.043)	(0.044)
House Rented (Market Rate)	0.056	0.018	0.033	0.017
	(0.054)	(0.048)	(0.047)	(0.049)
House Rented (Less Than Market Rate)	-0.015	0.138+	0.084	-0.015
	(0.077)	(0.072)	(0.069)	(0.070)
Rent-Free	-0.008	-0.177*	-0.016	0.122+
	(0.077)	(0.071)	(0.073)	(0.073)

HH Size	-0.009	0.067*	0.049	0.047
	(0.034)	(0.031)	(0.030)	(0.031)
Struggle To Pay Bills	-0.169***	-0.016	0.072*	0.019
	(0.038)	(0.035)	(0.035)	(0.035)
Negative EU Sentiment	-0.903***	-0.566***	-0.587***	-0.677***
	(0.043)	(0.041)	(0.041)	(0.041)
Car Owner	0.149***	-0.235***	-0.076*	0.021
	(0.041)	(0.039)	(0.037)	(0.038)
Don't Use Available Pub. Transport	0.222***	0.326***	0.379***	0.128**
	(0.047)	(0.042)	(0.041)	(0.041)
Num.Obs.	25788	25815	25803	25826
NUTS FE	X	X	X	X

Table 6. Coefficients from logistic regression models. Standard errors in parentheses. Baseline group corresponds to rural males in age group 15-24, lower secondary education, occupation group "Responsible for ordinary shopping, etc.", living arrangement "Owned by you, your household, without outstanding mortgage" and "no"/"not" responses for binary covariates where applicable. "Refusal" or "Don't know" categories are suppressed in the regression table output. + $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Responses of individuals that perceive themselves in energy consumption deciles 1 – 5 are fixed to decile 5.

	(1) Feel Personal Responsibility to Act	(2) Support Climate Tax	(3) Support Government Energy Quota	(4) Should do more against climate change regardless of others' efforts
Ranking	0.043*	0.027	0.067***	0.045**
	(0.019)	(0.017)	(0.016)	(0.017)
Urban	0.055	0.081*	0.073*	0.154***
	(0.039)	(0.035)	(0.034)	(0.035)
Age 25-34	0.033	0.224**	0.028	0.100
	(0.092)	(0.082)	(0.080)	(0.082)
Age 35-44	-0.039	0.152+	-0.071	0.074
	(0.092)	(0.082)	(0.080)	(0.082)
Age 45-54	-0.031	0.093	-0.072	0.021
	(0.091)	(0.081)	(0.080)	(0.082)
Age 55-64	-0.025	0.160+	-0.028	0.082
	(0.092)	(0.083)	(0.081)	(0.083)
Age 65+	-0.100	0.076	-0.073	0.015
	(0.101)	(0.091)	(0.089)	(0.091)
Female	0.361***	0.061*	0.211***	0.531***
	(0.034)	(0.030)	(0.029)	(0.030)
Post Sec. Educ.	0.348***	0.058	-0.097+	0.161**
	(0.064)	(0.056)	(0.055)	(0.057)
Primary or Lower Educ.	-0.539***	-0.331***	-0.342***	-0.107
	(0.083)	(0.079)	(0.079)	(0.082)

Tertiary Educ.	0.530***	0.224***	-0.102*	0.252***
	(0.060)	(0.054)	(0.052)	(0.053)
Upper Secondary Educ.	0.145**	0.101*	-0.002	0.079+
	(0.049)	(0.046)	(0.045)	(0.046)
Occ.: Student	0.247*	0.237*	0.156	0.196+
	(0.120)	(0.109)	(0.105)	(0.109)
Occ.: Unemployed	0.026	0.027	0.213*	-0.053
	(0.106)	(0.099)	(0.099)	(0.100)
Occ.: Retired	0.058	0.151*	0.145+	-0.006
	(0.082)	(0.076)	(0.075)	(0.077)
Occ.: Farmer	0.089	0.181	0.339*	0.203
	(0.174)	(0.166)	(0.167)	(0.169)
Occ.: Fisherman	1.231	0.097	0.778	1.115
	(0.791)	(0.582)	(0.697)	(0.704)
Occ.: Professional	0.101	-0.153	0.349**	-0.004
	(0.143)	(0.122)	(0.123)	(0.126)
Occ.: Shop Owner	0.010	0.039	-0.154	-0.172
	(0.124)	(0.116)	(0.112)	(0.117)
Occ.: Business Proprietor	0.024	-0.219+	-0.150	-0.219+
	(0.135)	(0.120)	(0.118)	(0.121)
Occ.: Empl. Professional	0.267*	-0.216*	-0.110	0.101
	(0.125)	(0.105)	(0.104)	(0.110)
Occ.: General Management	0.308+	-0.163	-0.055	-0.097
	(0.172)	(0.133)	(0.132)	(0.135)

Occ.: Middle Management	0.117	-0.122	0.140+	0.063
	(0.098)	(0.085)	(0.084)	(0.088)
Occ.: Employed (Desk)	0.132	0.013	0.120	0.009
	(0.089)	(0.080)	(0.079)	(0.082)
Occ.: Employed (Traveling)	0.006	-0.017	0.129	0.082
	(0.103)	(0.095)	(0.094)	(0.098)
Occ.: Employed (Service)	0.001	0.077	0.170*	-0.057
	(0.095)	(0.087)	(0.085)	(0.088)
Occ.: Supervisor	0.013	-0.008	0.075	0.114
	(0.139)	(0.129)	(0.127)	(0.130)
Occ.: Skilled Manual	-0.024	0.039	0.208**	-0.060
	(0.088)	(0.082)	(0.080)	(0.083)
Occ.: Unskilled Manual	-0.180+	-0.050	0.205*	-0.028
	(0.106)	(0.099)	(0.100)	(0.102)
House Owned	0.085+	-0.122**	-0.062	-0.052
	(0.051)	(0.044)	(0.043)	(0.044)
House Rented (Market Rate)	0.052	0.016	0.031	0.014
	(0.054)	(0.048)	(0.047)	(0.049)
House Rented (Less Than Market Rate)	-0.024	0.135+	0.077	-0.022
	(0.077)	(0.072)	(0.069)	(0.070)
Rent-Free	-0.010	-0.178*	-0.020	0.120
	(0.077)	(0.071)	(0.073)	(0.073)

HH Size	0.002	0.072*	0.055+	0.056+
	(0.034)	(0.031)	(0.030)	(0.031)
Struggle To Pay Bills	-0.175***	-0.019	0.067+	0.014
	(0.038)	(0.035)	(0.035)	(0.035)
Negative EU Sentiment	-0.914***	-0.571***	-0.592***	-0.686***
	(0.043)	(0.041)	(0.041)	(0.041)
Car Owner	0.167***	-0.227***	-0.067+	0.035
	(0.041)	(0.039)	(0.037)	(0.038)
Don't Use Available Pub. Transport	0.227***	0.327***	0.378***	0.131**
	(0.047)	(0.042)	(0.041)	(0.041)
Num.Obs.	25788	25815	25803	25826
NUTS FE	X	X	X	X

Table 7. Country-specific statistics on sample size, average perceived energy consumption decile, the standard deviation of the reported energy consumption deciles, a t-statistic when testing against the expected perfect information rank of 5.5, the share of respondents that place themselves in the median decile 5 and the average squared deviations from the expected perfect information 10% share across all ten deciles.

	Obs.	Avg. Decile	SD Decile	t Stat.	% Median	Avg. Sq. Dev.
AT	979	4.776	1.845	-12.271	0.257	0.076
BE	999	4.927	1.624	-11.150	0.342	0.099
BG	1003	4.748	1.609	-14.803	0.310	0.093
CY	502	4.918	1.848	-7.051	0.313	0.085
CZ	988	4.372	1.458	-24.315	0.374	0.115
DE	1495	4.396	1.463	-29.169	0.353	0.110
DK	996	4.404	1.665	-20.784	0.284	0.090
EE	986	3.998	1.706	-27.640	0.226	0.082
EL	1013	4.868	1.557	-12.928	0.311	0.095
ES	985	4.673	1.420	-18.273	0.357	0.107
FI	1037	4.311	1.840	-20.798	0.224	0.074
FR	966	4.384	1.626	-21.326	0.345	0.101
HR	996	5.014	1.584	-9.683	0.308	0.095
HU	1021	4.899	1.814	-10.587	0.328	0.092
IE	1013	5.042	1.578	-9.226	0.334	0.098

IT	1001	5.454	1.439	-1.021	0.269	0.101
LT	985	4.140	1.638	-26.053	0.316	0.094
LU	499	4.952	1.719	-7.124	0.297	0.088
LV	986	4.641	1.669	-16.164	0.359	0.101
MT	489	5.182	1.681	-4.183	0.329	0.095
NL	1031	4.484	1.832	-17.806	0.191	0.075
PL	1009	5.356	1.851	-2.475	0.312	0.086
PT	913	4.506	1.608	-18.677	0.324	0.097
RO	1046	5.330	1.671	-3.293	0.268	0.087
SE	1042	4.453	1.628	-20.756	0.298	0.092
SI	1004	4.052	1.857	-24.709	0.227	0.079
SK	983	4.719	1.521	-16.099	0.329	0.100

Table 8. Linear regression coefficients based on NUTS level model. Standard errors in parentheses. + p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

	Middle 40% Share	Bottom 30% Share	Top 30% Share
Urban	-0.024	0.011	0.013
	(0.031)	(0.024)	(0.019)
Coast	0.029	0.000	-0.007
	(0.026)	(0.020)	(0.016)
Mountain	0.038	-0.019	-0.014
	(0.051)	(0.040)	(0.031)
Num.Obs.	230	230	230
R2	0.344	0.454	0.175
R2 Adj.	0.249	0.375	0.055
R2 Within	0.009	0.002	0.003
R2 Within Adj.	-0.006	-0.013	-0.012
Country FE	X	X	X

Table 9. Coefficients from logistic regression models. Standard errors in parentheses. Baseline group corresponds to rural males in age group 15-24, lower secondary education, occupation group "Responsible for ordinary shopping, etc.", living arrangement "Owned by you, your household, without outstanding mortgage" and "no"/"not" responses for binary covariates where applicable. "Refusal" or "Don't know" categories are suppressed in the regression table output. + p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001.

	(1)	(2)	(3)
	Bottom 30%	Middle 40%	Top 30%
Age 25-34	0.053	-0.062	-0.002
	(0.097)	(0.087)	(0.165)
Age 35-44	0.258**	-0.214*	-0.060
	(0.098)	(0.088)	(0.165)
Age 45-54	0.375***	-0.317***	0.013
	(0.096)	(0.087)	(0.165)
Age 55-64	0.466***	-0.381***	-0.033
	(0.097)	(0.088)	(0.170)
Age 65+	0.536***	-0.470***	0.024
	(0.103)	(0.094)	(0.190)
Post Sec. Educ.	0.007	-0.022	0.038
	(0.061)	(0.057)	(0.121)
Primary or Lower Educ.	0.381***	-0.339***	-0.141
	(0.080)	(0.076)	(0.193)

Tertiary Educ.	-0.048	0.036	-0.007
	(0.058)	(0.054)	(0.115)
Upper Secondary Educ.	-0.089+	0.067	0.017
	(0.050)	(0.047)	(0.098)
Female	-0.076*	0.068*	-0.072
	(0.034)	(0.031)	(0.063)
Urban	-0.020	-0.032	0.161*
	(0.039)	(0.035)	(0.070)
HH Size	-0.410***	0.334***	0.072
	(0.034)	(0.032)	(0.064)
CC Frightens Me	-0.102**	0.066*	0.112
	(0.035)	(0.033)	(0.070)
Occ.: Student	-0.289*	0.211+	0.135
	(0.126)	(0.114)	(0.220)
Occ.: Unemployed	0.244*	-0.228*	-0.003
	(0.106)	(0.099)	(0.215)
Occ.: Retired	0.217**	-0.178*	-0.196
	(0.082)	(0.076)	(0.164)

Occ.: Farmer	-0.049	-0.083	0.377
	(0.194)	(0.170)	(0.287)
Occ.: Fisherman	-1.738	1.912+	-10.548
	(1.090)	(1.074)	(134.422)
Occ.: Professional	-0.131	0.048	0.175
	(0.142)	(0.129)	(0.246)
Occ.: Shop Owner	0.084	-0.154	0.270
	(0.130)	(0.118)	(0.226)
Occ.: Business Proprietor	-0.133	0.058	0.210
	(0.139)	(0.126)	(0.239)
Occ.: Empl. Professional	-0.070	0.086	-0.118
	(0.122)	(0.112)	(0.231)
Occ.: General Management	0.040	-0.063	0.094
	(0.156)	(0.141)	(0.263)
Occ.: Middle Management	-0.081	0.120	-0.219
	(0.098)	(0.090)	(0.183)
Occ.: Employed (Desk)	-0.254**	0.185*	0.004
	(0.093)	(0.084)	(0.162)

Occ.: Employed (Traveling)	-0.126	0.022	0.211
	(0.112)	(0.100)	(0.185)
Occ.: Employed (Service)	-0.196*	0.181*	-0.073
	(0.098)	(0.090)	(0.179)
Occ.: Supervisor	-0.249	0.202	0.011
	(0.158)	(0.141)	(0.258)
Occ.: Skilled Manual	-0.091	0.062	0.000
	(0.092)	(0.084)	(0.163)
Occ.: Unskilled Manual	0.132	-0.148	0.121
	(0.109)	(0.101)	(0.208)
House Owned	-0.065	-0.059	0.376***
	(0.051)	(0.046)	(0.086)
House Rented (Market Rate)	0.201***	-0.184***	0.001
	(0.052)	(0.049)	(0.108)
House Rented (Less Than Market Rate)	0.220**	-0.276***	0.345*
	(0.073)	(0.068)	(0.135)
Rent-Free	-0.083	-0.102	0.524***
	(0.084)	(0.074)	(0.129)

Struggle To Pay Bills	0.098*	-0.086*	0.032
	(0.039)	(0.036)	(0.072)
Negative EU Sentiment	0.347***	-0.304***	-0.041
	(0.045)	(0.043)	(0.096)
Car Owner	-0.529***	0.436***	0.222**
	(0.041)	(0.038)	(0.086)
Don't Use Available Pub. Transport	-0.327***	0.157***	0.283***
	(0.049)	(0.043)	(0.074)
Num.Obs.	25727	25844	23448
NUTS FE	X	X	X

Table 10. Coefficients from logistic regression models. Standard errors in parentheses. Baseline group corresponds to rural males in age group 15-24, lower secondary education, occupation group "Responsible for ordinary shopping, etc.", living arrangement "Owned by you, your household, without outstanding mortgage" and "no"/"not" responses for binary covariates where applicable. "Refusal" or "Don't know" categories are suppressed in the regression table output. + p < 0.1, * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001. The outcome of columns (1) and (2) is a binary variable indicating whether persons are "likely high consumers" (based on two different definitions), and respond they perceive themselves in the bottom 30% of energy consumers. Refer to the text for details.

	(1)	(2)
	Bottom 30% Excl. House Owners	Bottom 30% Incl. House Owners
Urban	-0.339*	-0.378*
	(0.149)	(0.171)
Age 25-34	-0.078	-0.181
	(0.423)	(0.593)
Age 35-44	0.458	0.470
	(0.407)	(0.567)
Age 45-54	0.390	0.331
	(0.406)	(0.562)
Age 55-64	0.425	0.392
	(0.408)	(0.568)
Age 65+	0.127	0.264
	(0.435)	(0.592)
Female	-0.123	-0.103
	(0.129)	(0.146)
Post Sec. Educ.	-0.406+	-0.195
	(0.234)	(0.278)

Primary or Lower Educ.	-0.362	-0.289
	(0.444)	(0.516)
Tertiary Educ.	-0.290	-0.210
	(0.226)	(0.271)
Upper Secondary Educ.	-0.223	-0.108
	(0.211)	(0.255)
Occ.: Student	-0.307	-0.053
	(0.632)	(0.863)
Occ.: Unemployed	-0.499	0.054
	(0.543)	(0.624)
Occ.: Retired	0.077	0.091
	(0.357)	(0.427)
Occ.: Farmer	-0.312	-0.021
	(0.689)	(0.748)
Occ.: Fisherman	-10.967	-10.507
	(335.798)	(337.323)
Occ.: Professional	0.005	-0.143
	(0.494)	(0.572)
Occ.: Shop Owner	-0.236	-0.426
	(0.468)	(0.572)
Occ.: Business Proprietor	-0.570	-0.418
	(0.483)	(0.547)

Occ.: Empl. Professional	-0.144	-0.096
	(0.440)	(0.509)
Occ.: General Management	0.139	0.194
	(0.466)	(0.539)
Occ.: Middle Management	-0.471	-0.401
	(0.386)	(0.457)
Occ.: Employed (Desk)	-0.502	-0.413
	(0.371)	(0.445)
Occ.: Employed (Traveling)	-0.062	0.042
	(0.400)	(0.484)
Occ.: Employed (Service)	-0.742+	-0.683
	(0.413)	(0.501)
Occ.: Supervisor	-1.408*	-2.821*
	(0.604)	(1.146)
Occ.: Skilled Manual	-0.489	-0.418
	(0.379)	(0.457)
Occ.: Unskilled Manual	0.050	0.587
	(0.528)	(0.599)
House Owned	0.029	0.025
	(0.173)	(0.186)
House Rented (Market Rate)	0.247	
	(0.221)	

House Rented (Less Than Market Rate)	-0.406	
	(0.374)	
Rent-Free	-0.090	
	(0.337)	
HH Size	-0.501***	-0.587***
	(0.136)	(0.159)
Negative EU Sentiment	0.393*	0.515*
	(0.197)	(0.229)
Num.Obs.	2673	2119
NUTS FE	X	X

Table 11. Detailed questionnaire questions and answers for the four variables related to climate action and policy support

Question code	Question	Possible answers
QA1.1	To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement: You feel a personal responsibility to act to limit climate change	Totally Agree (1), Tend to agree (2), Tend to disagree (3), Totally disagree (4)
	To what extent are you for or against the following policies in (OUR COUNTRY) to limit climate change in a way that it is inclusive and fair and leaves no one behind?	
QA16.2	Taxing products and services that contribute most to climate change, and redistributing revenues to the poorest and most vulnerable households	Strongly in favour (1), Somewhat in favour (2), Somewhat opposed (3), Strongly opposed (4)
QA16.3	Allocating a quota of energy to each citizen to ensure everyone makes their fair share of effort to tackle climate change	Strongly in favour (1), Somewhat in favour (2), Somewhat opposed (3), Strongly opposed (4)
	To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the green transition and the fight against climate change	
QA3.1	You should personally do more than you currently do to contribute to the green transition and tackling climate change (by consuming less or saving energy for example), regardless of what others do	Totally Agree (1), Tend to agree (2), Tend to disagree (3), Totally disagree (4)

Table 12. Detailed questionnaire questions and answers for the control variables used in the regression analyses.

Question code	Question	Possible answers
D9a	What is the highest level of education you completed?	No education completed, Primary school, Lower secondary education, Upper secondary education, Post-secondary non-tertiary education, Short cycle tertiary education, Bachelor or equivalent, Tertiary Degree, Master or equivalent, Tertiary Degree, Doctoral or equivalent.
D15a	What is your current occupation?	Responsible for ordinary shopping and looking after the home, or without any current occupation, not working ; Student ; Unemployed or temporarily not working ; Retired or unable to work through illness ; Self-employed farmer ; Self-employed fisherman ; Self-employed professional (lawyer, medical practitioner, accountant, architect, etc.) ; Owner of a shop, craftsmen, other self-employed person ; Business proprietors, owner (full or partner) of a company ; Employed professional (employed doctor, lawyer, accountant, architect) ; Employed position, general management, director or top management (managing directors, director general, other director) ; Employed position, middle management, other management (department head, junior manager, teacher, technician) ; Employed position, working mainly at a desk ; Employed position, not at a desk but travelling (salesmen, driver, etc.) ; Employed position, not at a desk, but in a service job (hospital, restaurant, police, fireman, etc.) ; Employed position, supervisor ; Employed position, skilled manual worker ; Other employed (unskilled) manual worker, servant
SD16	Which of the following applies to the place where you live?	Owned by you, your household, without outstanding mortgage ; Owned by you, your household, with outstanding mortgage ; You, your household are tenants or subtenants paying rent at market price ; You, your household are tenants or subtenants paying rent at reduced price ; Your accommodation is provided free, rent free ; Refusal
D40a/b/c,	How many people aged 15 years or more/children less than 10/ How many children aged 10 to 14 years old live in your household?	Numeric values

	live in your household, yourself included?	
D60	During the last twelve months, would you say you had difficulties to pay your bills at the end of the month...?	Most of the time ; From time to time ; Almost never/ Never ; Refusal
D78	In general, does the EU conjure up for you a very positive, fairly positive, neutral, fairly negative or very negative image?	Very positive ; Fairly positive ; Neutral ; Fairly negative ; negative ; don't know
SD13	Do you have a car?	Yes, diesel ; Yes, petrol ; Yes, hybrid ; Yes, electric ; Yes, other ; No, cannot afford ; No, other reason ; Refusal
Q11	On a typical day, what is your main mode of transport? By main mode, we mean the one that you use most often.	Car ; Car sharing (including taxi) ; Privately owned motorbike or moped ; Train (Non-urban) ; Ship or boat ; Public transport (bus, metro, tram, ferry, urban rail, etc.) ; Privately owned bike or scooter (including electric) ; Shared bike, scooter or moped (including electric) ; Walking ; No daily or regular mobility ; Other ; Don't know
QA12	<p>How would you rate the quality of public transport in the area where you live?</p> <p>In terms of availability: availability refers to the existence of sufficient public transport services to enable you to reach the places you need to go to, in terms of quantity and type.</p> <p>In terms of affordability, that is the money and time required to travel by public transport from one place to another.</p> <p>In terms of quality: quality means punctuality, cleanliness, safety, ease of access and comfort.</p>	Very good ; Fairly good ; Fairly bad ; Very bad.
QA3_1	To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the green transition and the fight against climate change?	Totally agree ; Tend to agree , Tend to disagree ; Totally disagree

<p>QA1_1</p>	<p>To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement : You feel a personal responsibility to act to limit climate change</p>	<p>Totally agree ; Tend to agree , Tend to disagree ; Totally disagree</p>
<p>QA16_2</p>	<p>To what extent are you for or against the following policy in (OUR COUNTRY) to limit climate change in a way that it is inclusive and fair and leaves no one behind?</p> <p>Taxing products and services that contribute most to climate change, and redistributing revenues to the poorest and most vulnerable households</p>	<p>Strongly in favour ; Somewhat in favour ; Somewhat opposed ; Strongly opposed</p>
<p>QA16_3</p>	<p>To what extent are you for or against the following policy in (OUR COUNTRY) to limit climate change in a way that it is inclusive and fair and leaves no one behind?</p> <p>Allocating a quota of energy to each citizen to ensure everyone makes their fair share of effort to tackle climate change</p>	<p>Strongly in favour ; Somewhat in favour ; Somewhat opposed ; Strongly opposed</p>

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